

Fluorescence Studies on some Bimetallic Tetradithiocarbamate Complexes

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*Manuscript received 16 August 1989,
revised 1 February 1991, accepted 8 April 1991*

FLUORESCENCE studies on some bimetallic tetradithiocarbamate complexes¹ of the type $MCuL_4$ ($M=Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}$; $L=N$ -ethyl cyclohexyldithiocarbamate) have been carried out. A number of photochemical parameters have been elucidated.

Experimental

Fluorescence studies were carried out on Jasco FP-550 spectrofluorometer. Sodium N -ethyl cyclohexyldithiocarbamate was prepared by the reported method².

Results and Discussion

In the fluorescence spectra the absorption band is observed at *ca.* 254 nm ($\log \epsilon \sim 4.3$) and the emission band at *ca.* 505 nm. Thus, in accordance with the Franck-Condon principle and thermal relaxation of vibrational modes, the fluorescence band is observed on the red side of the absorption band in approximately mirror-image relationship³.

In case of $HgCuL_4$ complex, however, the mirror image pattern is slightly disrupted with the appearance of a weak band at 300 nm ($\log \epsilon 1.6$). The appearance of this band may be traced back to the fact that the coupling of electron spin and orbital angular momentum is strong in atoms like mercury⁴. Due to this reason the clear distinction between the singlet and triplet states breaks down; the singlet states have a partly triplet character and the triplet states partly singlet character. The additional band thus arises due to the triplet $\rightarrow$ singlet transition, $Hg6(^3P_1) \rightarrow Hg6(^1S_0)$, which is forbidden by the rule prohibiting a change in multiplicity, $\Delta S=0$. Not only is the $\Delta S=0$ rule violated, but also the more

stringent requirement that the transition $J=0 \rightarrow J=0$ is not allowed. As a result, the 300 nm radiation is not absorbed by mercury atom and it is not a resonance line. However, atoms in the $6(^3P_1)$ state can be collisionally deactivated to the $6(^3P_0)$ state, and if no reverse activation step occurs the atom will stay in this metastable state until it finally emits the forbidden 300 nm radiation and returns to the ground state⁴.

The spectra are free from anti-stokes effects. The pattern of spectra follows Levschin's rule, indicating that the geometry of the excited state is not very different from that of the ground state⁵.

The actual radiative lifetime of the excited state (τ) is smaller than the intrinsic radiative lifetime (τ_0) indicating the possibility of non-radiating energy dissipation processes depopulating the excited state. Thus fluorescence remains the dominant but certainly not the exclusive mode of emission. The non-radiative processes, i.e. inter-system crossing and internal conversion compete with fluorescence. Therefore, Einstein's probability of spontaneous absorption, B_{nm} exceeds the corresponding probability of spontaneous emission, A_{mn} . The quantum yields of fluorescence, inter-system crossing and internal conversion follow the order: $\phi_f > \phi_{ISC} > \phi_{IC}$. These priorities are also established by their respective rate constants⁴.

The summation of rate constants for all the photochemical and photophysical processes competing with fluorescence, $\sum k_i$ equals the sum of K_{ISC} and K_{IC} . Thus apart from fluorescence, inter-system crossing and internal conversion, there seems to be no other mode of emission, radiative or non-radiative, in the present case⁵. The oscillator strength (f) has been calculated from the relation, $f = 4.31 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon \nu \bar{d\nu}$, which is valid if we assume Lorentzian shape for the absorption band. The factor $\int \epsilon \nu \bar{d\nu}$ is replaced by $\epsilon_{max} \Delta\nu$ where $\Delta\nu$ is the half band-width of the absorption band⁵. The data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FLUORESCENCE DATA OF COMPLEXES

Parameter	ZnCuL ₄	CdCuL ₄	HgCuL ₄
ϕ_f	0.53	0.57	0.55
ϕ_{ISC}	0.44	0.42	0.44
ϕ_{IC}	0.009	0.007	0.008
f	0.086	0.085	0.086
τ	0.50×10^{-8}	0.47×10^{-8}	0.48×10^{-8}
τ_0	0.94×10^{-8}	0.82×10^{-8}	0.87×10^{-8}
K_f (s ⁻¹)	1.06×10^8	1.21×10^8	1.14×10^8
K_{ISC} (s ⁻¹)	0.94×10^8	0.91×10^8	0.93×10^8
K_{IC} (s ⁻¹)	0.018×10^8	0.017×10^8	0.018×10^8
B_{nm}	2.9×10^8	3.0×10^8	2.9×10^8
A_{mn}	0.88×10^8	0.87×10^8	0.88×10^8

Conclusion : Of the three complexes, the CdCuL₄ complex has the maximum value of Einstein's absorption probability, B_{nm} . Accordingly, its rate constant of fluorescence emission (K_f) as well as the quantum yield of fluorescence (ϕ_f) are higher than the corresponding parameters of the ZnCuL₄ and

HgCuL₄ derivatives. The HgCuL₄ complex shows a weak band at 300 nm due to the interaction of the singlet and triplet states. In all the three cases, emission largely takes place by radiative phenomena. Nevertheless, the non-radiative processes, such as inter-system crossing and internal conversion also contribute.

References

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